

ROOTING ABILITY OF GOLDEN CURRANT CUTTINGS DEPENDING ON CUTTING DIAMETER AND PLANTING SCHEME

B.T. Ibragimov

Agronomist at Bukhara Scientific Experimental Station

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19230836>

Abstract. *This article studies the effect of planting schemes and cutting diameter on the rooting rate of golden currant (*Ribes aureum*) seedlings during propagation. During the research, experiments were carried out using different planting schemes (60×10 cm, 60×15 cm, 70×10 cm, and 70×15 cm) as well as different cutting diameters (3–4 mm, 5–6 mm, 7–8 mm, and 9–10 mm). According to the results of three years of observations, the highest indicator was recorded when using a 70×10 cm planting scheme and cuttings with a diameter of 5–6 mm.*

Keywords: *golden currant, seedling cultivation, cutting diameter, planting scheme, survival rate, rooting, agricultural techniques, propagation technology.*

Introduction

It is important to suggest that golden currant is among the plants of great importance due to its high nutritional value, medicinal properties, and productivity. In particular, currant varieties stand out for their adaptability to the soil and climatic conditions of Bukhara region and their high yield potential. Therefore, improving the technologies for its propagation is considered one of the important and relevant issues today.

Materials and Methods

When propagating golden currant seedlings, the planting scheme and the diameter of cuttings are considered important factors. These two factors influence not only the rooting rate, but also the quality development of seedlings in the future. The results of the experiment clearly demonstrated the relationship between these factors. According to the results of our experiment, the rooting ability of cuttings depending on their diameter and planting scheme was studied. In the 70×10 cm control planting scheme, 100 cuttings with a diameter of 7-8 mm were planted, and the average rooting indicators were determined differently across the years.

These indicators were determined as 59.5% in 2023, 65.7% in 2024, and 69.8% in 2025, with a three-year average of 65.0%. In the 60×10 cm planting scheme, due to the dense placement of cuttings, competition among plants increased. As a result, the rooting rate of the cuttings was relatively low. According to the results for the thinnest cuttings (3–4 mm), the rooting rate reached 48.5% in 2023, 53.6% in 2024, and 56.9% in 2025, with a three-year average of 53.0%.

For the slightly thicker cuttings (5–6 mm), the rooting rate was 64.5% in 2023, 71.3% in 2024, and 75.7% in 2025, reaching an average of 70.5%. For medium-thickness cuttings (7–8 mm), the indicator was 50.4% in 2023, 59.2% in 2024, and 55.1% in 2025. However, in the thickest cuttings (9–10 mm), the rooting rate was 50.2% in 2023, 55.5% in 2024, and 59.0% in 2025, with an average level of about 54.9%. Thus, under dense planting conditions, cuttings with a larger diameter adapt to rooting with greater difficulty, and the results decrease.

Results and Discussion

According to the experiment, the 60×15 cm planting scheme provided better rooting results because the plants had a larger nutrition area. The average rooting rate was 57.8% for cuttings with a diameter of 3–4 mm, 79.9% for 5–6 mm, and 64.9% for 7–8 mm. Even the largest cuttings (9–10 mm) showed a result of 60.6%. The 70×10 cm scheme produced the highest indicators in the experiment. Since this scheme ensured an optimal placement of cuttings, the competition between plants occurred at a normal level. As a result, the average rooting rate was 67.3% for cuttings with a diameter of 3–4 mm, 84.8% for 5–6 mm, and 54.3% for 9–10 mm. It is evident that this scheme ensured the highest level of rooting and survival of the cuttings.

In the 70×15 cm planting scheme, although the results were close to the control variant, slightly lower indicators were recorded. For example, the rooting rate was 68.3% for 3–4 mm cuttings, 77.4% for 5–6 mm, 63.6% for 7–8 mm, and 58.4% for 9–10 mm. This situation shows that excessively sparse planting can also create certain disadvantages. Overall analysis demonstrated that the most optimal results for golden currant seedlings were observed with the 70×10 cm planting scheme, especially when using cuttings with a diameter of 5–6 mm. Under very dense planting conditions, cuttings develop poorly due to strong competition, while in overly sparse planting the optimal balance of soil moisture and nutrition may be disrupted. Therefore, selecting the correct planting scheme and cutting diameter is one of the key factors for achieving high productivity in seedling cultivation (Table 1).

Effect of Cutting Thickness and Different Planting Schemes on the Rooting of Golden Currant Cuttings, % (2023–2025)

№	Planting Scheme, cm	Cutting Diameter, mm	Number of Cuttings Planted, pcs				Average Rooting Rate of Cuttings, %
				2023 y	2024 y	2025 y	
1	70x10 (назорат)	7-8	100	59,5	65,7	69,8	65,0
2	60x10	3-4	100	48,5	53,6	56,9	53,0
		5-6	100	64,5	71,3	75,7	70,5
		7-8	100	50,4	55,7	59,2	55,1
		9-10	100	50,2	55,5	59,0	54,9
3	60x15	3-4	100	52,8	58,4	62,0	57,8
		5-6	100	73,1	80,7	85,8	79,9
		7-8	100	59,4	65,6	69,7	64,9
		9-10	100	55,5	61,3	65,1	60,6
4	70x10	3-4	100	61,6	68,1	72,3	67,3
		5-6	100	77,6	85,7	91,1	84,8
		9-10	100	49,7	54,9	58,4	54,3
5	70x15	3-4	100	62,5	69,1	73,4	68,3
		5-6	100	70,9	78,3	83,2	77,4
		7-8	100	58,2	64,3	68,3	63,6

		9-10	100	53,4	59,1	62,7	58,4
	<i>RC05=</i>			<i>1,59</i>	<i>1,8</i>	<i>1,01</i>	<i>0,91</i>
	<i>RC%=</i>			<i>2,7</i>	<i>2,7</i>	<i>1,5</i>	<i>1,4</i>

Conclusion

As a result of the conducted research, it was determined that the planting scheme and cutting diameter are important agronomic factors in the propagation of golden currant cuttings. According to the experimental results, the highest rooting rate was recorded when using a 70×10 cm planting scheme and cuttings with a diameter of 5–6 mm. Very dense planting leads to strong competition between plants, which reduces the rooting rate. Conversely, excessively sparse planting can disrupt the balance of soil moisture and nutrient availability.

REFERENCES

1. Kalinin F.L., Merezhinsky Yu.G. Plant Growth Regulators: Biochemistry, Mechanism of Action and Application. – Kyiv: “Naukova Dumka”, 2012. – 115 p.
2. Sukhovetskaya V.A., Kystaubaeva A.S. Promising Black Currant Varieties and Methods of Their Propagation // East Kazakhstan Research Institute of Agriculture (Ust-Kamenogorsk), Kazakhstan. – 2015. – p. 154–156.
3. Skaliy L., Samoshchenkov E.G. Propagation of Plants by Green Cuttings. — Moscow: MSHA Publishing, 2002. — 115 p.
4. Timusheva O.K., Zainullina K.S. Influence of Growth Regulators on Rooting of Green Cuttings of Black Currant Varieties during Cultivation // Russian Journal of Fruit and Berry Growing. 2011. Vol. 28, No. 2. P. 257–264.
5. Yurina L.V. Garden Innovations. Moscow: Astrel Publishing LLC, 2002. – 272 p.